

MENTAL HEALTH OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO WORK PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 8

Pages: 903-911

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3015

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14998674

Manuscript Accepted: 01-22-2025

Mental Health of Junior High School Teachers in Relation to Work Performance: Basis for Intervention

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Abstract

The purpose of this study entitled “Mental Health of Junior High School Teachers in Relation to Work Performance: Basis for Intervention” was to examine the mental health of junior high school teachers in relation to their work performance for School Year 2021-2022. A Survey Questionnaire for Mental Health was administered to 164 respondents Junior High Teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School and their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form was the basis for their work performance. To know the level of mental health, the mean was used and interpreted as very high, high, average, low, and very low. The results showed that the respondents have high level of mental health and outstanding work performance. It was also found out that the level of mental health of the teachers was not affected by their profile. Based on the results of gamma, it has been found that there is no significant relationship between the levels of mental health and work performance of the junior high teachers.

Keywords: *mental health, work performance, intervention*

Introduction

Within the dynamic field of education, teachers hold a crucial position in molding the minds and future of the next generation. Despite receiving years of training to become adaptable and versatile, teachers can still become unprepared for unforeseen changes and challenges in the classroom.

The stress of their work and the growing complexity of today's educational system have drawn attention to the issues with mental health that educators face. This specific health concern is an important but frequently disregarded factor that has a big impact on their overall work output, job satisfaction, performance, productivity, and the standard of instruction they give their clientele (Corrente, Ferguson & Bourgeault, 2022).

Teachers deal with mental health issues on the same level as all employees in various field of work. The demands and obligations they have, both at home and at school, have an effect on their well-being according to Children's Mental Health Ontario (2020). Meanwhile, it is essential to understand the complex relationship between teachers' mental health and their productivity at work to establish supportive conditions in educational settings. Several research works have demonstrated a robust association between improved job performance and favorable mental health outcomes (Burić & Macuka, 2020). On the other hand, untreated mental health conditions have been connected to teacher attrition, lower productivity, lower performance, and absenteeism (Johnson, Kraft, & Papay, 2018).

In this study, the researcher wanted to determine the relationship of the mental health of junior high teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School towards their work performance.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship of the mental health of junior high teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School in their performance during the pandemic. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender
 - 1.2. Length of Service
 - 1.3. Monthly Income
 - 1.4. Grade Level
 - 1.5. Subject Taught
2. What is the level of mental health of teachers as a whole and when grouped according to profile?
3. What is the work performance of the junior high teachers as a whole and when grouped according to level of mental health?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the mental health of junior high teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School in their work performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to know the mental health level of junior high teachers in Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School in

relation to their work performance. Thus, the researcher used a descriptive research design.

Descriptive research was used to describe the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It will not answer the questions how, when, and why the characteristics occurred. Rather, it will address the question what and it can be either quantitative or qualitative.

Descriptive research is an exploratory method that allows researchers to systematically describe a population, circumstance, or phenomenon. This method of research involves the collection of data in order to test the hypotheses or answer questions concerning the current status of the subject under study (Singh, 2023).

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the 164 junior high teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School who were teaching during the School Year 2021-2022.

Total population sampling, a type of purposive sampling, was employed in this research. Purposive sampling is utilized in research studies to choose a particular group of individuals or units for analysis. This method is suitable when the researcher has a clear idea of the characteristics they want to study and aims to select a sample that is representative of those characteristics (Heath, 2023). Thus, all 164 junior high teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School were the respondents.

Instrument

Part I. The first part of the instrument used in this study was to gather the profile of the respondents. This included their gender, length of service, gross monthly income, grade level taught, and subject matter taught.

Part II. In terms of work performance, the instrument used was the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), a standardized assessment tool from the Department of Education. This tool is used to evaluate teachers for their yearly accomplishments. They were rated as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor.

Part III. The data-gathering instrument used to assess the mental health of teachers was adapted from the Mental Health Self-Assessment Questionnaire designed by Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS) from the University of Warwick and University of Edinburgh (2006). It was a standardized 15-item questionnaire and each statement were rated as 5 – All of the time, 4 – Often, 3 – Some of the time, 2 – Rarely; and, 1 – None of the time.

Procedure

To gather data, the researcher sought approval from the Principal and Assistant Principal of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School. After being approved, the researcher sought permission from the respondents to conduct a survey.

After the availing the approval, the researcher distributed the survey forms personally to the respondents which are the junior teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School for the school year 2021-2022. The survey forms were collected immediately by the researcher to secure confidentiality of information after giving enough time for the respondents of the study to accomplish it.

Data Analysis

After the data were gathered, the researcher tallied, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted the data. In the analyses and interpretation of data, different statistical tools were used:

To answer statement of the problem no. 1 which states, what is the profile of teachers in terms of gender, length of service, monthly income, and grade level, frequency and percentage were used.

To answer statement of the problem no.2 which states, what is the level of mental health of teachers as a whole and when grouped according to profile, frequency and mean were used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 3 which states, what is the performance of the junior high teachers as a whole and when grouped according to level of mental health, frequency and mean were used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 4 which states, is there a significant relationship between the mental health of junior high teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School and their work performance, gamma was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analyses and interpretation of data gathered for this study.

Profile of Junior High School Teachers

The table below shows the profile of the junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School for S.Y. 2021-2022.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution on the Profile of Junior High School Teachers*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender	Male	36	28.10
	Female	92	71.90
	Total	128	100.00
Length of Service	Below 6 Years	18	14.10
	6-10 years	41	32.00
	11-15 years	27	21.10
	16-20 years	17	13.30
	more than 20 years	25	19.50
	Total	128	100.00
Monthly Income	below P30,000	69	53.90
	P30,000-35,000	40	31.30
	P36,000-40,000	2	1.60
	more than P40,000	17	13.30
	Total	128	100.00
Grade Level	Grade 7	30	23.40
	Grade 8	29	22.70
	Grade 9	35	27.30
	Grade 10	34	26.60
	Total	128	100.00
Subject Taught	Math	18	14.10
	Science	19	14.80
	MAPEH	16	12.50
	TLE	20	15.60
	AP	12	9.40
	ESP	8	6.30
	Filipino	17	13.30
	English	18	14.10
	Total	128	100.00

The table shows the frequency distribution of the profile of the respondents. It presents that there were 36 male teachers or 28.10 percent of the population were male and there were 92 female teachers or 71.90 percent of the population were female. As to the length of service, 18 teachers or 14.10 percent have been teaching for six years and below, 41 teachers of 32 percent have been teaching for 6-10 years, 27 teachers or 21.10 percent have been teaching for 11-15 years, 17 teachers or 13.30 percent have been teaching for 17 years, and 25 teachers or 19.50 percent have been teaching for more than 20 years.

As to the monthly income, there were 69 teachers or 53.90 percent of the teachers have below Php 30 000 income, 40 teachers or 31.30 percent of the teachers have income of Php 30 000 – Php 35 000, 2 teachers or 1.60 percent have income of Php 36 000 – Php 40 000, and 17 teachers or 13.30 percent of the teachers have income of more than Php 40 000.

There was a total of 30 teachers from Grade 7 or 23.40 percent, 29 were from Grade 8 or 22.70 percent, 35 teachers from Grade 9 or 27.30 percent, and there were 34 teachers from Grade 10 or 26.60 percent. 18 teachers were teaching Math which is 14.10 percent, 19 teachers were teaching Science which is 14.80 percent, 16 teachers were teaching MAPEH which is 12.50 percent, 20 teachers were teaching TLE which is 15.60 percent, 12 teachers were teaching Araling Panlipunan which is 9.40 percent, 8 teachers were teaching ESP which is 6.30 percent, 17 teachers were teaching Filipino which is 13.30 percent, 18 teachers were teaching English which is 14.10 percent.

This shows that more female teachers were teaching in Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School. At the same time, most of the teachers are in the service for 6-10 years and more than half of the population are earning below P30,000. Meanwhile, more teachers are assigned for Grade 10 and the ESP subject has lesser personnel.

Level of Mental Health of Junior High School Teachers And their Profile

The table below shows the level of mental health of the junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School for S.Y. 2021-2022.

The table presents that 36 male teachers and 39 female teachers have both high levels of mental health with means of 3.94 and 4.14 respectively.

For length of service, 18 teachers have worked below 6 years and have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.03. Out of 128 teachers, 41 teachers have worked for 6-10 years and have a high level of mental health with a mean of 3.98. There were 27 teachers

who have worked for 11-15 years and have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.10. 17 teachers who have worked for 16-20 years have a very high level of mental health with a mean of 4.31 and 25 teachers who have worked for more than 20 years have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.13.

Table 2. *Level of Mental Health of Junior High School Teachers as a whole and when grouped according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Gender	Male	36	3.94	High
	Female	92	4.14	High
Length of Service	Below 6 years	18	4.03	High
	6-10 years	41	3.98	High
	11-15 years	27	4.10	High
	16-20 years	17	4.31	Very High
	More than 20 years	25	4.13	High
Monthly Income	Below P30,000	69	4.05	High
	P30,000-P35,000	40	4.09	High
	P36,000-P40,000	2	4.17	High
	More than P40,000	17	4.22	Very High
Grade Level	Grade 7	30	4.10	High
	Grade 8	29	3.98	High
	Grade 9	35	4.09	High
	Grade 10	34	4.16	High
Subject Taught	Math	18	4.01	High
	Science	19	3.96	High
	MAPEH	16	4.17	High
	TLE	20	3.99	High
	AP	12	4.22	Very High
	ESP	8	4.03	High
	Filipino	17	4.20	High
	English	18	4.16	High
As a Whole		128	4.09	High

For monthly income, 69 teachers who have a monthly income below P30,000 have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.05. 40 teachers who have a monthly income of P30,000-35,000 have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.09. There were two teachers who had a monthly income of P36,000-P40,000 and had a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.17. Out of 128 teachers, the 17 teachers who had more than P40,000 monthly income and had a very high level of mental health with a mean of 4.22.

The 30 teachers from Grade 7 have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.10 while the 29 teachers from Grade 8 have a high level of mental health with a mean of 3.98. The 35 teachers from Grade 9 who have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.09 while the 34 teachers from Grade 10 also have a high level of mental health with a mean of 4.16.

Meanwhile, the 18 Math teachers have garnered a mean score of 4.01, 19 Science teachers have a mean score of 3.96, 16 MAPEH teachers have a mean score of 4.17, 20 TLE teachers have a mean score of 3.99, 8 ESP teachers have a mean score of 4.03, 17 Filipino teachers have a mean score of 4.20, and 18 English teachers have a mean score of 4.16 which are all interpreted as high level of mental health. However, the 12 Araling Panlipunan teachers have shown a very high level of mental health with a mean score of 4.22. As a whole, a mean score of 4.09 was garnered by the 128 teachers which is interpreted as a high level of mental health.

The junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School have a high level of mental health regardless of their gender, length of service, monthly income, grade level taught, and subject matter taught which is a good manifestation that includes the absence of social dysfunction, anxiety, and conditions.

The result is in consonance to the study of Rosenfield and Mouzon (2018) which stated that male and female teachers have varying levels of mental health. The results of their study also indicated that their gender, though different, does not have relation to their mental health. Mental health issues affect men and women differently. Men display more externalizing disorders, such as substance misuse and antisocial behavior, which are problematic for others, than women do internalizing diseases like sadness and anxiety. Studies pertaining to gender and mental health indicate that perceptions of masculinity and femininity impact significant risk factors for internalizing and externalizing issues, such as the stressors that men and women encounter, the coping mechanisms they employ, the social connections they make, and the vulnerabilities and personal resources they cultivate.

Rosenfield and Smith (2018) also added that many studies demonstrate that there are no overall differences in the rates of psychopathology between men and women when considering all psychological disorders combined. It follows that in terms of total mental health, neither gender is worse off than the other.

The result is also related to the study of Corrente, et. al. (2022) which stated that having poor mental health at work is strongly linked to poor psychological outcomes, low job satisfaction, absenteeism, and quitting intentions. This means that some can shorten their length of services in employment if they experience issues with their mental health. Employees in good mental health can specifically increase cognitive flexibility and solve more challenges in professional assignments.

According to Piketty (2020), social conditions are thought to play a significant role in driving mental health burden and increasing health inequalities. Income may be particularly important, as those with lower incomes may find it more difficult to maintain a sense of control or security over their lives and most importantly, income is also amenable to policy intervention.

Meanwhile, it is less clear whether raising someone's income will improve their mental health, despite the fact that low income is clearly associated with poor mental health. Individuals with poor mental health are more likely to suffer subsequent income losses, suggesting the possibility of reverse causation or health selection (Owsu-Addo, Renzaho, & Smith, 2018).

The result is opposite to the study of Jones-Rincon and Howard (2019) where they found out that given the added demands of their jobs, teachers on lower grade levels frequently feel and report higher levels of stress than higher grade level instructors (Jones-Rincon & Howard, 2019). Teachers are frequently expected to assist students in developing both cognitive and noncognitive skills, as well as to comprehend the relationship between practice and research. Additionally, they must accommodate the unique needs of each student, deliver fair outcomes in classrooms with a growing diversity, and quickly adjust to technological advancements in the classroom (Potter, 2021).

On the study of Luine, et. al. (2018), both internal and external influences may have an impact on the mental health of teachers. Heavy workloads, subject taught, a lack of administrative assistance, inadequate facilities and educational environments, a shortage of staff, and a lack of mental health training are examples of external issues. Life stresses, such as money or marital issues, as well as unique personality qualities and coping techniques, can all be considered internal causes (Luine, et. al., 2018).

Agarwal (2023) also stated that teachers' rigorous workloads are one of the main issues affecting their mental health. In addition to teaching, teachers are frequently required to balance a heavy workload that includes substantial planning and administrative work. The wide range of behavioral issues that teachers deal with in the classroom is another important element that has an impact on their mental health. Teachers must skillfully negotiate the multiplicity of behaviors and personalities that each student brings to the classroom.

Work Performance and Level of Mental Health of Junior High School Teachers

The table next page shows the work performance of the junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School for S.Y. 2021-2022.

Table 3. *Level of Work Performance of Junior High School Teachers as a whole and when grouped according to Level of Mental Health*

<i>Level of Mental Health</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean of Teaching Performance</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	41	4.6207	Outstanding
High	74	4.5962	Outstanding
Moderate	13	4.5409	Outstanding
Low	0	-	-
Very Low	0	-	-
As a Whole	128	4.5945	Outstanding

The table shows that there were 41 teachers who have very high level of mental health and have a mean of 4.62 in teaching performance which is interpreted as outstanding. There were 74 teachers who have high level of mental health and have a mean of 4.5962 in teaching performance which is interpreted as outstanding. Lastly, there were 13 teachers who have moderate level of mental health and have a mean of 4.5409 in teaching performance and is interpreted as outstanding.

As a whole, the 128 teachers who have moderate to very high level of mental health have a mean of 4.5945 in teaching performance which is interpreted as outstanding.

The junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School have outstanding level of work performance and have good mental health.

While striving for perfection is a commendable quality, it may also put a great deal of strain on educators. An atmosphere of increased anxiety and stress can be brought about by the pressure to accomplish academic goals, continually uphold high standards, and produce extraordinary outcomes (Agarwal, 2023).

Additionally, teachers are more likely to attest to higher dedication, which includes outstanding performance, to sticking with the industry and stronger motivation at work. It is crucial to realize that bettering working conditions can help to keep and even draw in new teachers to the teaching profession (Bakker et al., 2018).

These studies demonstrate that there are no overall differences in the rates of psychopathology between men and women when considering all psychological disorders combined. It follows that in terms of total mental health, neither gender is worse off than the

other (Rosenfield and Smith, 2018).

Relationship between Level of Work Performance and Level of Mental Health

The table below shows the relationship between the level of work performance and level of mental health of the junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School for S.Y. 2021-2022.

Table 4. Relationship between Level of Work Performance and Level of Mental Health of Junior High School Teachers

Level of Mental Health	Level of Teaching Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Poor	
Very High	35	6	0	0	0	41
High	60	14	0	0	0	74
Moderate	9	4	0	0	0	13
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	104	24	0	0	0	128

Computed value (G): 0.23

P-value: 0.260

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that 35 outstanding teachers have a very high level of mental health, 60 outstanding teachers who have high level of mental health, and 9 outstanding teachers who have moderate level of mental health. Also, 6 very satisfactory teachers have very high level of mental health, 14 very satisfactory teachers have high level of mental health, and there were 4 very satisfactory teachers who have moderate level of mental health.

Upon using Gamma, a computed value of 0.23 was obtained which is lower than the P-value which is 0.260 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the level of work performance and the level of mental health of teachers.

It was found that the junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School have outstanding work performance and high level of mental health.

These two are significantly related and teachers can perform their duties and responsibilities for their students regardless of the levels of their mental health.

Concerns about the connection between worker mental health and productivity have been prevalent in the workplace. The limited results of current research, however, stem from their emphasis on the contexts of developed economies and the ambiguous nature of the relationship between employee mental health and performance (Lu, et. al., 2022).

The results, however, contradict the study of Cao, et. al. (2022) where they found put that the correlation between the psychological well-being of employees and their job performance has emerged as a significant area of their study. According to academic research, workers in good mental health will be more enthusiastic and exhibit a positive work state, while workers in poor mental health may become inactive at work and experience a decline in interpersonal relationships, both of which have a negative effect on workers' productivity (Cao, et. al., 2022).

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings of this research study, the conclusions that were arrived at are as follows:

There were more female junior high teachers in the school, more teachers teaching for 6-10 years, more teachers earning below P30,000, more teachers in Grade 10, and more teachers teaching the TLE subject.

The junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School have high level of mental health.

The junior high school teachers of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School have outstanding work performance level.

The level of mental health of teachers is not affected by their gender, length of service, monthly income, grade level, and subject taught.

The level of work performance of teachers is not affected by their level of mental health.

As per the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

It is recommended that teachers identify common problems causing mental health concerns and participate in activities that promote mental well-being and resilience, even among those who are already doing well.

Teachers are encouraged to pursue professional development opportunities in their areas of expertise, which may include workshops, conferences, or online courses related to innovative teaching methods, curriculum development, or educational technology.

School leaders are advised to introduce programs that encourage a healthy balance between work and personal life to sustain high performance and well-being in the long term. These initiatives may include flexible work arrangements, wellness programs, or family-friendly policies.

It is recommended that researchers continue to find other issues, challenges, and concerns that may be related in the overall performance of teachers.

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